

Strategic Design for the Development of Emotional Intelligence in Preschool Education

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
<p>Published Online: 30 October 2025</p> <p>Corresponding Author: Ingrid Elideth Pérez Delgadillo</p>	<p>This article analyzes the importance of the development and management of Emotional Intelligence (EI) in preschool-aged girls and boys. It begins with the recognition that emotions directly influence learning, social behavior, and personal well-being, making it crucial to address them from the early stages. The main objective was to understand and identify the level of emotional management in children within the classroom and, based on this, to identify and suggest effective strategies for emotional development, supported by current references and the pedagogical experience of preschool teachers.</p> <p>The methodology used was mixed (quantitative-qualitative), involving the application of a reliable instrument, as well as a documentary review of international, national, and regional authors from 2020 to 2024.</p> <p>The results highlight that play-based activities, storytelling, behavior modeling, and emotional routines implemented by teachers are highly effective tools to promote the development and management of EI. This article concludes that when planned and systematic strategies and activities are considered and integrated into the preschool curriculum and practice, they promote the development of soft skills such as self-control, empathy, and emotional self-regulation.</p>
<p>KEYWORDS: Emotional Intelligence, preschool education, emotional management, socioemotional development, soft skills.</p>	

INTRODUCTION

Currently, as a result of the dynamism in human development, emotional education has acquired a fundamental role in the early levels of teaching, especially in preschool. Emotions play a key role in the regulation and management of social relationships, the attitude and disposition towards learning, as well as in the formation of self-concept in the early years of life (Bisquerra, 2020). In this context, emotional intelligence (EI), understood as the ability to recognize, understand, and manage one's own and others' emotions (Goleman, 1995), is positioned as a key 21st-century life skill.

We can note that early emotional development not only prevents behavioral problems but also strengthens skills in empathy, resilience, and conflict management and resolution. However, there are still gaps and shortcomings in teacher training, curriculum planning, and practical strategies aimed at emotional intelligence in the preschool stage. (Extremera & Fernández-Berrocal, 2022).

This intervention project is framed within the need to strengthen emotional development from preschool, based on research and theoretical models such as those of Daniel Goleman and Howard Gardner, adapted to the context of

early childhood. Through the design of structured, contextualized, and validated strategies, it aims to promote the recognition of emotions, empathy, and self-control in children, in close collaboration with the school environment. This paper proposes an educational intervention that integrates theory and practice, prioritizing qualitative and quantitative analysis through the application of reliable instruments for information gathering. In this case, the reliability of the instrument was validated using Cronbach's Alpha algorithm, allowing the project to continue by analyzing the impact and significance of emotional education at the preschool level, and enabling the suggestion of some strategies designed for this purpose.

It is an innovative and sensitive approach, aimed at transforming the educational experience into a platform for emotional growth, laying the foundations for empathetic, critical, and emotionally competent citizenship.

General Objective

To promote the development of emotional intelligence in students through an intervention program that encourages the proper expression of emotions, as well as empathy, in order to achieve effective self-regulation and emotional management.

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Specific objectives

- ▶ Identify the factors that influence the emotional development of girls and boys through the application of a contextualized diagnostic instrument.
- ▶ Design pedagogical strategies aimed at developing emotional intelligence, focusing on the proper expression of emotions and empathy.
- ▶ Implement the designed strategies through educational activities that promote emotional self-regulation and the strengthening of the school environment.

METHODOLOGY

According to Sampieri, the quantitative research method is characterized by being objective, systematic, and statistical. Its purpose is to measure phenomena, establish relationships between variables, and test hypotheses through the use of standardized instruments and numerical data. It is based on the collection and analysis of quantifiable data to generalize results to a larger population.

The project proposes the design and implementation of specific strategies for the development of emotional intelligence at the preschool level. These strategies will be aimed at strengthening students' recognition and management of emotions, integrating playful activities, participatory dynamics, and teacher training.

The Likert scale is a widely used measurement instrument in surveys and quantitative studies to assess people's attitudes, opinions, or perceptions on a specific topic. It is an ordinal rating scale that presents a series of statements to which the respondent must indicate their level of agreement or disagreement using predefined options.

In Figure 1, we show the results for the entire preschool level with 19 students who have low emotional development and require priority attention, as they still have difficulties identifying, expressing, and managing their emotions. The intervention should focus on establishing basic emotional routines that create a predictable and supportive environment. These activities should be permanent and visible throughout the daily schedule, respecting each child's pace and always promoting inclusive participation with the rest of the group. We have 56 students with average emotional development: they are able to identify some emotions, show occasional empathy, and can resolve simple conflicts with guidance.

Finally, we have 17 students with high emotional development. These students already demonstrate autonomy in emotional management, advanced empathy, and positive leadership within the group. They can become role models or mediators in certain activities if their participation is properly guided.

Figure 1. Scale of values

Level of Intervention	Values
Underdeveloped emotionally	19
Average emotional development	56
High emotional development	17

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

- Girls and boys begin to identify basic emotions (joy, sadness, anger, fear) more accurately.
- The use of emotional vocabulary in everyday situations was promoted, strengthening affective communication.
- During the project, moments of frustration were identified, and techniques to calm down were proposed.
- An increase in prosocial behaviors such as sharing, comforting, and cooperating was observed.
- Interpersonal conflicts were reduced, and the peaceful resolution of disagreements was promoted.

The reliability analysis was conducted on an assessment instrument for emotional development, applied to a sample of 93 students.

The questionnaire consists of 12 items formulated using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = Never, 5 = Always).

3. Instrument data:

- Number of items: 12
- Number of participants: 93
- Scale type: Likert (1 to 5 points)
- Purpose of the instrument: To measure the level of emotional development

4. Formula used:

$$\alpha = (k / (k - 1)) \times [1 - (\sum \text{Var}(i) / \text{Var}(\text{total}))]$$

Where:

- α = Cronbach's Alpha
- k = Total number of items
- $\text{Var}(i)$ = Individual variance of each item

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• $\text{Var}(\text{total}) = \text{Variance of the total sum of each participant}$

5. Obtained result:

$\alpha = 0.859$ This value indicates high internal consistency, which validates the reliability of the instrument.

6. Interpretation:

According to reliability criteria:

- 0.90 or more = Excellent
- 0.80 – 0.89 = Very good
- 0.70 – 0.79 = Acceptable
- Less than 0.70 = Low or questionable

With a value of 0.859, it is concluded that the questionnaire has very good reliability for assessing emotional development in students, and is therefore considered a valid instrument for the study.

The previous analysis allows verification that the items of the instrument are indeed reliable and measure the construct of emotional intelligence, so that it can be better developed in children and they can identify, express, and manage their emotions.

By including this coefficient, the project demonstrates that the measurement tool has been validated, which strengthens the consistency of the results obtained. Based on the conclusions described above, it is suggested: to train educational staff in the use of emotional strategies, as well as to monitor their implementation, recording observations and progress.

By including this coefficient, the project demonstrates that the measurement tool has been validated, which strengthens the consistency of the results obtained. Based on the conclusions described above, it is recommended to: Train educational staff in the use of emotional strategies, as well as to monitor their implementation, recording observations and progress. The strategies suggested for the continuation of the project are:

Strategies for Emotional Education

1. Emotional regulation routines: Meditation, guided breathing, sensory games.
2. Emotional stories: Tales with dilemmas to help children identify their emotions.
3. Role-playing games: Simulation of social situations to foster empathy.

The strategies previously suggested will be implemented based on the following follow-up actions:

Follow-up and implementation actions

- Conduct teacher feedback sessions to adjust pedagogical practices.
- Create emotional portfolios for each student with drawings, reflections, and participation records.
- Document outstanding cases of emotional development for qualitative analysis.

Las estrategias anteriormente sugeridas se implementarán con base a las siguientes acciones de seguimiento:

- Integrate models such as Goleman's, Gardner's, and the Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) approach to enrich the foundation.

- Implement emotional workshops for parents and caregivers to reinforce what is practiced in the classroom.

- Create practical guides for home that promote emotional routines.

- Ensure that the strategies consider the emotional, cognitive, and social diversity of the students.

CONCLUSION

The development and management of emotional intelligence in the preschool stage should be understood as an integral, educational, human, and contextually relevant process; for this reason, the results and findings confirm the importance and significance of cultivating and developing key emotional skills for life from an early age (early childhood). Achieving this will require focused and specialized teacher training, an open attitude, human sensitivity, appropriate teaching resources and infrastructure, as well as planning that considers and incorporates emotional education into the daily development of preschool education.

This work confirms the importance of addressing emotional control from an early age as a fundamental part of the educational process, promoting the development of more conscious human beings who are capable of managing their emotions. (Reference from the NEM). This is relevant because of the guidelines and goals of the New Mexican School regarding the emotional development of girls and boys.

The application of a mixed methodology (quantitative and qualitative approach) allowed for the objectification of results and precise measurement, providing valuable information for future educational interventions, from a standpoint of accuracy and reliability, while also offering a human and emotional perspective that leads the reader to reflect on the impact of education in emotional development as a life approach and the balance between well-being and daily performance.

Through the application of a questionnaire designed to assess these aspects and whose reliability was verified using Cronbach's alpha coefficient (obtaining a value of greater than or equal to), the consistency of the items was ensured, and therefore, the validity of the collected data. The results allow us to generate a series of ideas and recommendations to reflect on the knowledge, development, and application of emotional intelligence.

Based on what has been developed in this project, we can conclude that socio-emotional development in early childhood is fundamental for the construction of meaningful learning, healthy relationships, and a balanced identity. This intervention project allowed us to confirm that the design and implementation of strategies for the identification, management, and emotional control at the preschool level not only promotes emotional self-regulation in children but also strengthens the school climate, coexistence, and conflict resolution capacity. Finally, it is suggested to continue the project through the periodic implementation of observation

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and measurement instruments, as well as the implementation of other similar diagnostic elements, along with the inclusion of qualitative techniques that enrich the understanding of the results and allow for a comprehensive response to the needs identified at the preschool level.

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